

Original Articles

Towards standardized ecosystem condition assessments: Selecting agroecosystem condition indicators based on SEEA EA with an example application in Lower Saxony, Germany

Emily Bank^{a,*}, Sabine Lange^a, Bálint Czúcz^b, Malte Hinsch^a, Benjamin Burkhard^a

^a Institute of Earth System Sciences, Leibniz University Hannover, Schneiderberg 50, 30167 Hannover, Germany

^b Norwegian Institute for Nature Research, Høgskoleringen 9, 7034 Trondheim, Norway

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ecological condition
Ecosystem characteristics
Selection criteria
Croplands
Grasslands
Degradation
Restoration

ABSTRACT

Human well-being strongly relies on agroecosystems in good condition to ensure food security and a sustainable Ecosystem Services (ES) supply. However, agroecosystems face growing threats from environmental pressures, increasing the need for conservation and restoration measures. Their targeted and efficient implementation requires reliable, comprehensive and standardized methods to assess and monitor agroecosystem condition. To support such integrated assessments, we aimed to identify a set of suitable agroecosystem condition indicators.

We applied the UN System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA), to support standardized assessments. In a literature review, we identified the most relevant agroecosystem characteristics based on expert knowledge and current practice. Subsequently, we applied the SEEA EA selection criteria to filter the most suitable indicators and datasets under conceptual and practical aspects. Finally, we mapped the selected indicators and checked the entire set for redundancies. We used the Federal State of Lower Saxony (Germany) as an exemplary study area, including both agricultural croplands and grasslands.

The review revealed 19 relevant physical, chemical, compositional, structural, functional and landscape agroecosystem state characteristics. The subsequent filtering process resulted in a comprehensive set of nine ecosystem condition indicators.

The selected indicators are suitable to support comprehensive agroecosystem condition assessments for various purposes. However, high-resolution data availability remains a key limiting factor, restricting the suitability of the selected indicators to regional-scale assessments. While the indicator set already can support monitoring procedures, future research is needed to define reference levels and to calculate condition indicators with a normative meaning.

1. Introduction

Human well-being strongly relies on agroecosystems in a good Ecosystem Condition (EC) to ensure food security and the sustainable supply of essential Ecosystem Services (ES) (Maes et al., 2018). The good condition of agroecosystems, however, is increasingly at risk due to a growing number of environmental pressures, including global climate change, land degradation and biodiversity loss. Policy makers increasingly acknowledge the importance of agroecosystems and the threats they face and increasingly focus on their conservation, restoration, and sustainable development. However, despite the need for targeted management, conservation and restoration measures, common methods for

agroecosystem condition assessments are lacking (European Commission, 2024).

Agroecosystems represent the terrestrial ecosystem types with the largest coverage worldwide, covering a total of almost 40 % of the global land surface with croplands and grasslands (Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, 2021). Aiming at the production of food, fodder and other fiber-/biomass-related products, they result from human-induced targeted modifications of natural ecosystems (Maes et al., 2018). Traditional low-intensity agricultural management practices have fostered the development and maintenance of unique floral and faunal communities and habitat conditions, thereby supporting biodiversity and the supply of multiple highly relevant ES (Piqueray

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: bank@phygeo.uni-hannover.de (E. Bank).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113813>

Received 28 February 2025; Received in revised form 24 June 2025; Accepted 24 June 2025

Available online 27 June 2025

1470-160X/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

et al. 2011; Maes et al., 2018; Lombardo et al., 2020), which benefit both the productive areas and adjacent ecosystems. Being highly dependent on many regulating ES like soil erosion control, pollination or water filtration themselves, agroecosystems play a dual role as both suppliers and users of ES (Zhang et al., 2007; Granata et al., 2023).

When agroecosystems maintain biodiversity and promote a stable ES supply, they are considered in good condition (Maes et al., 2018; Vallecillo et al., 2022). However, agricultural intensification increasingly threatens these conditions, by causing soil degradation, disrupted nutrient and water cycles, pollution and species loss (Ruiz-Martinez et al., 2015; Rendon et al., 2022). These impacts extend beyond the productive areas to the surrounding ecosystems, reducing the quality and quantity of ES supply, and accelerating biodiversity loss (Ruiz-Martinez et al., 2015; Naturkapital Deutschland - TEEB DE, 2016; Vallecillo et al., 2022). Given the large share of agricultural land worldwide, restoring and maintaining the good condition of agroecosystems is a critical global environmental and societal concern.

Policy makers and institutions globally increasingly acknowledge the role of agriculture as both, driver of environmental degradation and a major arena for ecosystem conservation, restoration and biodiversity promotion (Rendon et al., 2022). The European Union (EU) has brought the sustainable development of agriculture to support environmental protection efforts to the focus of its Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the EU Green Deal and the associated policies. “Improving the condition [...] of agroecosystems [to] increase the sector’s resilience to climate change, environmental risks and socioeconomic shocks” (European Commission, 2020, 2.2.2) is among the objectives of the EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030. But, although recognized in different legislations, agroecosystems are not adequately addressed in environmental laws, compared to other ecosystem types (Vallecillo et al., 2022). Thus, spatially explicit and reliable indicators on agroecosystem condition are still limited, but urgently needed for both descriptive and normative purposes, to identify priority areas for conservation and restoration efforts and to monitor and evaluate their effectiveness.

Quantifying and interpreting agroecosystem condition is especially challenging due to strong anthropogenic influences and the clear focus on production (i.e. one single provisioning ES) in these systems. Various approaches have been developed which differ in the basic understanding of EC, in the socio-cultural character of agroecosystems and in the purpose of the assessment. This is reflected in the choice of EC indicators and related indicator sets, which range from inherent system characteristics (e.g., Zobeck et al., 2007; Jastrezebska et al., 2009; Little et al., 2015; Gedoz et al., 2021) to external pressures (e.g. Hess et al., 2000; Rendon et al., 2022; Hinsch et al., 2024), focus on specific system components (Blumetto et al., 2019) or include a range of characteristics (e.g., Sinclair et al., 2015; Kirch et al., 2016) and show different spatio-temporal complexities (Hess et al., 2000; Xu et al., 2019). The selected indicators significantly influence the results and conclusions regarding EC (Keith et al., 2020). This complicates the comparability of assessments, especially since the method of selection is not always transparently justified (Maes et al., 2020; Czúcz et al., 2021b). Some studies show a bias towards policy-relevant indicators and many indicator choices appear to be data-driven (Maes et al., 2020; Vallecillo et al., 2022), which sets another limit on the reliability of results.

Efforts have been made to standardize EC assessments and EC accounting. The EU working group on Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (MAES) has defined EC as the ‘physical, chemical and biological condition of an ecosystem at a particular point in time’ (Maes et al., 2018, p. 11) and provides lists of indicators to assess EC and pressures per ecosystem type. In 2021, the United Nations adopted the System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA), which defines EC as ‘the quality of an ecosystem measured in terms of its biotic and abiotic characteristics’ (United Nations (UN) et al., 2024, 5.2). The SEEA EA framework provides guidelines for three subsequent stages of an EC assessment with a clear distinction between descriptive condition variables and normative

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the SEEA EA ecosystem condition assessment stages and additional preconditions (based on UN et al., 2024). Stage 1 and the previous step are at the focus of this work. For definitions of the SEEA EA-specific terms in italics, see Box 1.

condition indicators (see Fig. 1 & Box 1 for terminology) while keeping interpretations flexible. The EU, in response to the UN’s call to implement SEEA EA in its member states (King et al., 2024), is currently modifying its EC mapping and assessment methodology in order to be consistent with this recently accepted global standard (Vallecillo et al., 2022).

Given the clear structure and guidelines, SEEA EA offers one possible approach to address the challenges in assessing and quantifying agroecosystem condition. But, although there are ambitions to establish SEEA EA as a global assessment standard, the framework has not yet been widely recognized and adopted (Nature, 2020; Edens et al., 2022). This limited adoption may be partly due to its relatively recent introduction, but also to the broad scope and (intended) flexibility of the framework and the consequent lack of concrete EC indicators, which might delay uptake. Pilot EC assessments have been conducted in different ecosystem types, which revealed both conceptual challenges and data gaps (Farrell et al., 2021; Maes et al., 2023; Ryan et al., 2023). On agroecosystems, SEEA EA condition assessments have been implemented in exceptional cases on grasslands and abandoned farmland (Maes et al., 2020; Parkhurst et al., 2024).

Therefore, with this study, we aimed to identify a minimum set of suitable agroecosystem condition indicators in a structured and transparent way by applying the SEEA EA principles to support the standardization of ecosystem assessments. Consequently, in the paper, we will use the terms ‘variable’ and ‘indicator’ following the SEEA EA terminology and use ‘metrics’ when referring to both (see Box 1 for detailed definitions). Precisely, we aimed to provide (i) an overview of the most relevant agroecosystem characteristics and suitable EC variables for their description and (ii) ready to use datasets of EC variables for a spatially explicit agroecosystem condition assessment. The study was thus focused on the first stage of the SEEA EA approach (Fig. 1). We identified characteristics that should be universally relevant for all types of agroecosystems and selected and tested these selected EC variables exemplarily for the German Federal State of Lower Saxony to answer the following research questions:

- Which are the most relevant agroecosystem characteristics to consider?
- How can the SEEA EA selection criteria be applied for the selection of suitable EC variables?
- Which EC variables are suitable to describe the characteristics and support a comprehensive agroecosystem condition assessment in a regional-scaled case study?
- Are the selected EC variables transferable to other study areas and what are the limitations?

Box 1

Key terms related to ecosystem condition assessments (Source: [United Nations](#), [European Union](#), [Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations](#), [International Monetary Fund](#), [Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development](#), [The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank](#), 2024 unless indicated otherwise).

Ecosystem accounting: Organizing biophysical information on ecosystems, measuring ecosystem services, tracking changes in ecosystem extent and condition, valuing ecosystem services and assets and linking this information to measures of economic and human activity (p. 3).

Ecosystem assets: Contiguous spaces of a specific ecosystem type characterized by a distinct set of biotic and abiotic components and their interactions (para 2.11).

Ecosystem characteristics: The system properties of the ecosystem and its major abiotic and biotic components (water, soil, topography, vegetation, biomass, habitat and species) (para 5.28).*

Ecosystem condition: The quality of an ecosystem measured in terms of its abiotic and biotic characteristics (para 2.13).**

Ecosystem condition indices: (in SEEA EA context) Composite indicators that are aggregated from the combination of individual ecosystem condition indicators recorded in the ecosystem condition indicator account (para 5.81).

Ecosystem functioning: The operating or performance of an ecosystem, often involving a normative context implying a 'proper functioning' ([Potschin et al., 2014](#)).

Ecosystem health: The capacity of an ecosystem to maintain its organization and autonomy over time and to resist external pressures in relation to a desired (sustainable) reference condition or target ([Rendon et al., 2019](#)).

Ecosystem integrity: An ecosystem's capacity to maintain composition, structure, functioning and self-organization over time within a natural range of variability (para 5.10).

Ecosystem services: The contributions of ecosystems to the benefits that are used in economic and other human activity (para 2.14).

Indicators: (1) (in SEEA EA context) Ecosystem condition indicators are rescaled versions of ecosystem condition variables (para 5.60).*** (2) Indicators in the common understanding are observed value representatives of a phenomenon of interest, used to describe and evaluate states or changes and to set objectives. In general, indicators quantify information by aggregating different and multiple data (based on [Gabrielsen & Bosch, 2003](#); [Heink & Kowarik, 2010a](#)).

Normative (statement): An evaluation of a feature of the world as good or bad, better or worse, relative to some standard or alternative, or a statement reflecting how things ought to be ([Czúcz et al., 2021b](#)).

Reference levels: The values of a condition variable against which it is meaningful to compare measured values of the variable. Reference levels are used to rescale a condition variable to derive an indicator ([Czúcz et al., 2021b](#)).

Variables: (1) (in SEEA EA context) Ecosystem condition variables are quantitative metrics describing individual characteristics of an ecosystem asset (para 5.41).*** (2) Variables in the common understanding are characteristics or quantities of a phenomenon of interest that are liable to or capable of taking on different possible values ([Ofem & Mchi, 2023](#)).

*In EC assessments, *ecosystem characteristics* are the targeted *indicanda* to be described by condition variables and indicators.

***Ecosystem state* is considered to be a synonym of *ecosystem condition* in this study.

***We use the term *metric* when referring to both variables and indicators.

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of the three methodological steps for the selection of EC variables within the SEEA EA assessment stage 1 (Fig. 1). SEEA-EA selection criteria refer to [United Nations](#), [European Union](#), [Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations](#), [International Monetary Fund](#), [Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development](#), [The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank](#), 2024 and [Czúcz et al. \(2021\)](#).

2. Materials and methods

We combined literature work and data work in three main steps. First, we conducted a comprehensive literature review in order to generate a list of candidate variables that could potentially be used to assess agroecosystem condition. In this step we also identified and grouped the underlying ecosystem characteristics for each candidate variable (step Pre-1 in Fig. 2). Subsequently, we applied a two-stage filtering and prioritization process on the ecosystem characteristics and concrete candidate variables, applying the conceptual and practical selection criteria recommended by SEEA EA (UN et al., 2024) and described more in detail by Czúcz et al. (2021b). The global literature review conducted in step Pre-1, along with the universally applicable conceptual criteria, lead to a set of commonly suitable EC variables for agroecosystems. Within the boundaries of this common set, we applied the practical criteria to identify respective study area specific datasets that could potentially be applied for the quantification of variables. We then used the selected datasets to produce spatial maps of the selected EC variables in Lower Saxony (Stage 1a in Fig. 2). Finally, we revised the comprehensive set of EC variables for redundancies (Stage 1b in Fig. 2).

2.1. Case study area to test the set of variables

The German Federal State of Lower Saxony covers around 48,000 km² and is located in the north-west of Germany, bordering the North Sea (Heunisch et al., 2017). As large parts belong to the Atlantic biogeographical region, it is characterized by a relatively warm temperate and humid climate (Condé et al., 2002; Schönwiese, 2013). Various landscape types and diverse nature regions are located in the region, including the Wadden Sea and the marshlands at the coast, the Geest, numerous peatlands and the heathland in the North German Plain and the Lower Saxon Hills in the south.

Lower Saxony is under intensive agricultural use, with a share of 58 % of the area in 2023. This makes the region one of the main contributors to the German agricultural sector and one of the most agriculturally productive areas worldwide (Blickensdörfer et al., 2022; Destatis, 2024). Agriculture in the region benefits from the combination of large plain areas covered by fertile sedimentary deposits and the comparably mild climate (Blickensdörfer et al., 2022). However, intensive land use causes significant modification and fragmentation of prevailing ecosystems.

The agricultural area contains roughly two thirds of arable land and one third of grassland, and a minor share of permanent cultures, such as orchards. Cereals are cultivated the most in terms of area, followed by green harvest crops (LSN, 2024). Crop production varies regionally, with potatoes primarily grown on the sandy soils of the Heathland, sugar beets cultivated in the Börde regions and fruits and vegetables concentrated very locally, for instance in the 'Altes Land' region near river Elbe. Grasslands are prevalent in the coastal regions with their high groundwater levels and frequent flooding (Fig. 3). Livestock farming is another important part of the agriculture (NML, 2010). The different types of production are reflected in varying farm sizes between a few and several hundred hectares (LSN, 2024). Given these diverse and regionally varying patterns with an overall intensive land use, Lower Saxony is well-suited as an exemplary case study area to assess agroecosystem condition.

2.2. Identification of relevant agroecosystem characteristics

An EC assessment initially requires the selection of the most relevant ecosystem characteristics to be included and described (UN et al., 2024). Thus, we started with a global literature review exploring how frequently the different condition characteristics have been proposed, assuming that a higher frequency of use is a possible indication of relevance (Czúcz et al., 2021b).

We retrieved relevant scientific literature from the online databases

Web of Science and Scopus. In the search string, we combined one of the terms 'agroecosystem*', 'agriculture*', 'arable land', 'grassland*', 'pasture*', 'crop*', 'cultivat*' with one of the terms 'condition*', 'ecosystem* state', 'ecological state', 'ecosystem* health', 'ecological health', 'integrity' in the title or keywords and the term 'indicator*' in the abstract (we used the * wildcard to include all variations of the terms). Here we used the term 'indicator' in a general sense to cover all kinds of quantitative metrics of different complexity that are used to describe agroecosystem characteristics. No restrictions regarding the year or type of publication and the study area were set in the search. We applied the PRISMA scheme for systematic literature reviews (Page et al., 2021) to the primary list to identify the publications to be reviewed in several consecutive steps. Based on the search strings we identified a total of 1,049 publications in the two databases. After the removal of 390 duplicates and 77 non-English language papers, we screened the abstracts of the remaining 582 publications for eligibility. We removed another 516 unsuitable publications from the list in this step and we finally also excluded 14 publications that were neither openly accessible nor available upon request. In the subsequent full text screening, we excluded further five publications that were review papers or only dealt with EC indicators from a theoretical perspective without concrete suggestions and one publication which focused on olive orchards only. The process resulted in 46 papers included in the analysis, the complete list of which can be found in S1.

From the selected papers, we extracted the EC variables in a database of 'candidate variables' and classified them according to the SEEA EA Ecosystem Condition Typology (ECT), thus into physical (A1), chemical (A2), compositional (B1), structural (B2), functional (B3) or landscape (C1) state variables. We sorted the remaining variables into an additional class labelled 'ancillary data' (Czúcz et al., 2021a; United Nations, European Union, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, International Monetary Fund, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank, 2024). As a next step for each candidate variable we identified an 'underlying' ecosystem characteristic, i.e. we tried to define and classify those properties of the agroecosystems that the candidate variables in the reviewed studies were aiming to quantify, following an interpretive synthesis approach (Dixon-Woods et al., 2006; see Box 2). This resulted in a list of "commonly assessed" agroecosystem characteristics nested under the ECT typology, which could also be seen and treated as "ECT subclasses". For instance, within the A2 (chemical state) class, we grouped the variables 'electric conductivity', 'sodium adsorption rate' and 'exchangeable sodium percentage' to describe the characteristic 'soil salinity/sodicity', while 'nitrogen content', 'phosphate content' and 'calcium content' were grouped to describe 'soil nutrient status' (Table S1).

Subsequently, we analyzed the frequency of application of the individual characteristics. From each ECT class, we considered the three most often applied characteristics to be universally relevant and included them in the following steps. We conducted the frequency analyses separately for cropland and grassland studies to acknowledge the different ecosystem types' functioning.

2.3. Selection process for agroecosystem condition variables

Not all ecosystem characteristics, regardless of their relevance for ecological processes, can serve as equally meaningful EC indicators. Therefore, the SEEA EA framework provides a list of conceptual and practical selection criteria to apply on ecosystem characteristics and their metrics. However, the requirements for each criterion have not been precisely defined but must be determined depending on the study purpose. Additionally, verification usually relies on extremely fragmented and difficult-to-synthesize expert knowledge (Czúcz et al., 2021b; UN et al., 2024).

Therefore, in this study, we implemented the selection approach suggested by Czúcz et al. (2021) and UN et al. (2024) in a concrete case

Fig. 3. Case study area location in Germany (a) and agricultural land use types and nature regions in Lower Saxony (b). Based on [Schwieder et al. \(2024\)](#) and [Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal and Nature Protection Agency \(2011\)](#).

Box 2

Interpretive synthesis to define agroecosystem characteristics.

To identify a list of “ecosystem characteristics” that are addressed by groups of condition variables, we performed an inductive-deductive interpretive synthesis ([Thomas & Harden, 2008](#); [Bhattacharjee, 2012](#)), combining flexible, data-driven decisions with previous assumptions in an iterative workflow. By synthesizing the expert knowledge available in the reviewed literature in this way, we aimed to (1) create simple and coherent groups of characteristics, which (2) capture the relevant differences between the variables, (3) while keeping alignment with SEEA EA.

We started with identifying clear common “themes” among a subset of the variables which served as an initial list of ecosystem characteristics. Then we gradually added new variables and refined the classification in an iterative process, adjusting the assignment of the variables as new groups emerged ([Dixon-Woods et al., 2006](#)). We did not aim at a uniform level of detail, but reacted flexibly to both qualitative and quantitative patterns within the variables ([Macura et al., 2019](#)). We applied the following principles during the iterations:

**SEEA EA compliance: the list of characteristics had to be nested under the ECT classes.

**Focus on compartments: we aimed to distinguish variables describing the different main ecosystem components (like soil, groundwater, aboveground vegetation etc.).

**Flexible thematic resolution: a higher number and diversity of candidate variables implied a higher thematic resolution, i.e. we made more nuanced distinctions in such “popular” parts of the typology (e.g. we distinguished soil ‘exchange capacity’, ‘salinity/sodicity’ and ‘acidity’, previously summarized in a ‘soil fertility’ group, due to the range of salinity and acidity-related metrics).

**Measurement units: Where it made sense, we also used measurement units of the variables to sub-classify the characteristics (e.g. ‘vegetation cover’ expressed in areal or percentage units, ‘vegetation density’ expressed in density units).

study by applying the selection criteria in an efficient way. We determined the order based on the ease of criteria verification, allowing to filter out unsuitable EC variables at an early stage to minimize research efforts for the remaining criteria. Additionally, we made a distinction between ‘enabling criteria’ and ‘quality criteria’. Based on this, we divided the selection process into two consecutive steps as described in the following.

In the first step, we applied an exclusion process. We classified the criteria considered in this step as essential prerequisites for the

suitability of an EC variable, enabling a SEEA EA-aligned assessment. If the applied criterion was not fulfilled, we excluded the characteristic (and the related EC variables) immediately. The criteria applied in the second step determine the quality of the remaining EC variables, rather than the absolute suitability for an assessment. Here, we did not exclude EC variables immediately after each application of a criterion, but sorted them according to their quality for each criterion. After evaluating all criteria within this step, we excluded the EC variables with the overall lowest quality in a deliberation process. After all EC variables passed

through the process individually, we revised the resulting set regarding the SEEA EA ensemble criteria (Fig. 4).

The following sections provide a description on how each criterion was determined and verified for this study.

2.3.1. Application of the enabling criteria

- (1) *Intrinsic relevance* points to the general importance of a characteristic for ecosystem functioning. The verification requires a broad understanding of the studied ecosystem type's functioning (Keith et al., 2013), that can be retrieved in an expert deliberation (Czúcz et al., 2021b). We did not set further specifications or requirements but considered the criterion fulfilled by default, assuming that the relevant expert knowledge was already compiled in the literature review and the classification of the EC variables (see 2.2) to a sufficient extent.
- (2) *Framework conformity* ensures the integrity in the SEEA EA context by avoiding overlaps with other framework components and mismatches among the categories of the underlying DPSIR¹ framework. For verification, an understanding of the wider framework context is necessary, but some examples of particular critical variables are provided by the framework (e.g. climate variables rather describe drivers than the state) (Czúcz et al., 2021a; UN et al., 2024). We carefully checked the correct assignment of the variables to the framework components during

the review and sorted non-conforming variables in the ancillary class (see 2.2.), thus we considered the criterion fulfilled by default.

- (3) *Sensitivity to human influence* aims for EC variables that respond to changed pressures or management activities on human time-scales, making them useful for policy- and decision-making (Czúcz et al., 2021b). Verification requires respective expert knowledge of the temporal behavior of natural variables. To address this, we carried out a targeted search in the respective scientific literature.
- (4) *Data availability* is perhaps the most important practical prerequisite for an EC assessment implementation and remains a strong limiting factor (Czúcz et al., 2021; Lange et al., 2022). To identify relevant available data, the required spatial and temporal scale, coverage and resolution must be set depending on the study area and purpose (Czúcz et al., 2021b). We conducted an online data inventory, compiling both datasets providing ready-to-use measurement units and raw input data for subsequent processing. For this, we set the minimum spatial resolution to 10 km, excluding also spatially over-aggregated data, and the temporal limit to data not predating 2013.
- (5) *Validity* refers to the credible and unbiased representation of characteristics by the selected EC variables, which is of particular importance as ecosystem assessments rely on proxies to a large extent (Czúcz et al., 2021b). Explicit validity requirements have not been specified by SEEA EA, but must be set according to the study purpose. We ensured valid representation of characteristics (1) content-wise, by retaining only EC variables that are clearly contained in the respective characteristic, such as species richness as part of biodiversity (Noss, 1999) and (2) spatially, by excluding spatially aggregated data, detached from the underlying (spatial) ecosystem characteristic, as misleading display may cause a biased representation (Crossmann, 2017).
- (6) *Instrumental relevance* points out to the relevance of a characteristic for the availability of ES. Verification requires respective expert knowledge on ecosystem characteristics and ES relationships, which is available, however fragmented and partly contradictory (Czúcz et al., 2021b). We conducted brief semi-structured literature searches, combining the terms [name of characteristic/variable] AND [Ecosystem Services] in different search engines and applying a snowball technique from the initial results. We spent a similar amount of time on each characteristic to treat each equally despite evident differences in the available knowledge base.
- (7) The *directional meaning* refers to the possibility of interpreting the EC variables in a normative ("good" vs. "bad") context. To ensure this, expert consensus is required about whether a change would lead to an improvement or deterioration of the EC (Czúcz et al., 2021b). To determine this, we carried out a targeted search in the respective scientific literature.

Fig. 4. Schematic illustration of the selection process for EC variables based on SEEA EA selection criteria (Czúcz et al., 2021b; UN et al., 2024) applied in two steps distinguishing enabling and quality criteria.

2.3.2. Application of the quality criteria

After checking for enabling criteria, we compared the available datasets with regards to their quality in terms of three practical criteria:

- (8) *Reliability* aims at the reproducibility and accuracy of the selected metrics. It can be achieved by a high spatial resolution and timeliness of datasets as well as by the use of primary data instead of modelled data, because the latter one might hold a risk of error accumulation (Burgass et al., 2017; Czúcz et al., 2021b). We collected the relevant information for our compiled datasets and, based on these, ranked the datasets' overall reliability.
- (9) *Compatibility* targets the consistency of different accounts across ecosystem types and assets (Czúcz et al., 2021b; Moriarty et al., 2018; Schmeller et al., 2018). It requires knowledge of suitable EC variables for other ecosystem types, for which in-depth

¹ Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (Gabielsen & Bosch 2003).

research is necessary. We did not cover all ecosystem types in the scope of this study but considered the criterion by favoring EC variables that are suitable for both of our studied land use types, croplands and grasslands. Additionally, we preferred datasets that cover larger spatial extents, which allow for a broader application.

- (10) *Simplicity* refers to the communication and reporting of the assessment results to a broader audience. The perception strongly depends on the targeted users. It is, however, recommended to generally avoid qualitative or categorical variables but to use variables with statistical properties instead (Czúcz et al., 2021b). We followed these recommendations and, where applicable, favored well-established metrics.

It must be noted that the selection criteria refer to the final variable metric rather than to the raw datasets. Thus, where possible, we preferred datasets that provide the final quantification units of variables to avoid an additional level of uncertainty. Where there was only basic data for subsequent variable calculation available, we applied (where possible) the criteria (1) to the basic dataset and (2) considered them while calculating the final quantification units. For instance, to keep spatial explicitness as validity criterion, to calculate ‘crop species richness’ from a crop types map, we conducted a neighbourhood analysis in a moving window, instead of an aggregation across administrative units. However, some criteria might be further improved, by constructing more suitable EC variables from available datasets (e.g. using more suitable statistical parameters, improved models, better interpolation techniques).

2.3.3. Application of the ensemble criteria

The ensemble criteria of *comprehensiveness* and *parsimony* refer to the suitability of the entire set of EC variables and can thus only be verified with a number of previously selected variables. However, *comprehensiveness* should not only be considered at the end of the selection, but throughout the process (Czúcz et al., 2021b). The criterion aims at the full coverage of all relevant ecosystem characteristics (Niemeijer & de Groot, 2008). Nevertheless, SEEA EA also sets a weaker expectation (a “minimum level of comprehensiveness”) by demanding that “at least one variable is selected for each of the six ECT classes” (UN et al., 2024, 5.46).

We considered comprehensiveness already in the first step by selecting the most frequent EC variables per ECT class instead of the most frequent ones overall. Doing so, we avoided bias towards certain often applied characteristics, such as chemical soil characteristics. We acknowledged comprehensiveness again in the second selection stage during the deliberation process, where we excluded lower-quality EC variables only if at least one other was retained in the respective ECT class.

The criterion of *parsimony* aims at applying a minimal number of indicators while including the most possible information on the investigated system (Czúcz et al., 2021b). This facilitates appropriate assessments while keeping data collection and processing efforts low (UN et al., 2024). Moreover, smaller indicator sets minimize interpretation difficulties, (potentially) ensuring the quality and clarity of results (Kwatra et al., 2020). We accomplished parsimony by identifying potentially correlated variables, which add only little information and carry the risk of double-counting or double-weighting (Nardo et al., 2005; Hämäläinen & Alaja, 2008; Niemeijer & de Groot, 2008). After mapping the selected EC variables, we calculated Spearman’s correlation coefficient ρ using R software. We chose rank correlation due to its better applicability to non-normally distributed and discrete data, which applied to some of the variables. To manage the large dataset resulting from the study area’s size and the high resolution, we performed the analysis on a randomly distributed sample of 10 % of the cells that showed a valid cell entry across all variables. We set the threshold for the exclusion of a variable to $\rho \geq 0.7$, corresponding to a strong correlation

according to Schober et al. (2018).

2.4. Spatial calculation of selected condition variables

The selected datasets were processed in ArcGIS Pro to calculate and map the EC variables in the desired quantification units. We mainly compiled datasets displaying the final measurement units of the variables, so only minor adjustments were required in most cases, such as clipping to the study area’s extent or resampling of raster data to the smallest available resolution of 10 m. More extensive spatial calculations were needed only in a few cases (Table S2).

3. Results

3.1. Relevant agroecosystem characteristics

The literature review revealed more than 200 metrics that are used to assess EC of croplands and grasslands globally. The complexity varied from comparably concrete EC variables (e.g. ‘Bulk density [g/mL]’ and ‘Cation exchange capacity [meq./100 g]’ in Bedolla-Rivera et al., 2020), to broader characteristics (e.g. ‘Subsoil compaction’ in Sanderson, 2014; ‘Soil fertility’ in Wang et al., 2009). After the grouping of EC variables, they covered nine physical state characteristics, six chemical state characteristics, four compositional state characteristics, eight structural state characteristics, seven functional state characteristics and five landscape state characteristics as depicted in Fig. 5.

Notably, both physical and chemical state characteristics are predominantly soil-related, with few exceptions. ‘Soil structure’ and ‘water regime’ are the two most frequently used physical characteristics in both cropland and grassland studies, followed by ‘soil compaction’ respectively ‘soil stability’. The most frequent chemical state characteristics, namely ‘soil nutrient status’, ‘soil organic matter’ and ‘soil salinity/sodicity’ are consistent across both land use types, which also applies to the class of compositional state characteristics. ‘Plant community characteristics’ were most frequently used in both cropland and grassland studies, with the high frequency of use in grassland studies being particularly remarkable across all results.

Structural state characteristics reveal more differences between the two land use types, both in terms of the most frequent characteristics and the characteristics’ distribution. In cropland studies, ‘cropping pattern’ (including spatial and temporal aspects of crop distribution) was by far the most frequently considered characteristic, while in grassland studies, it was ‘ground cover’, though with less divergence from other characteristics. A similar pattern was observed in functional state characteristics: cropland studies focus on ‘microbial functionality’, whereas grassland studies also consider ‘plant health’. Other functional characteristics were also frequently considered in grasslands, however they were not regarded as relevant here, as the class encompasses miscellaneous unspecific variables. Among landscape state characteristics, the ‘presence of semi-natural elements’ was most relevant across both ecosystem types.

All applied cropland characteristics were also recognized in grassland studies. In contrast, grassland studies revealed some highly specific characteristics that were not examined in croplands. These include ‘mammal community characteristics’ (B1), ‘vegetation density’ and ‘plant structural traits’ (B2), ‘reproductivity’ and ‘functional group characteristics’ (B3), as well as ‘landscape connectivity’ and ‘patch characteristics’ (C1). However, these differences may be due to the unequal distribution of cropland and grassland studies in our review, which also explains the large differences in absolute numbers shown in Fig. 5. While we identified only 15 suitable cropland studies, we included 45 in the grassland analysis. Of these, we included 14 studies in both, as they addressed both ‘croplands’ and ‘grasslands’ in their study areas or referred to agroecosystems without further specification.

This initial result yields the 19 characteristics listed in Table 1, which are the most relevant ones based on application frequency either in

Fig. 5. Frequency of application of ecosystem characteristics in the reviewed studies. A total of 46 studies were included, out of which 15 were considered in the cropland analysis and 45 in the grassland analysis. Darker tones indicate the (up to) 3 most relevant characteristics per ECT class. Where there were more than 3 with similar frequency, the number was reduced respectively. *Total value = 86 (exceeds scale).

cropland or grasslands and which were the starting point for the filtering process.

To address uncertainties related to the grouping of EC variables, their frequency of use was additionally analyzed independently. Even though some are applied very frequently and many only sporadically, the identification of the most relevant EC variables was less straightforward, as distortions towards a few common characteristics are evident. However, there is generally a tendency for the most frequently used EC variables to align with the relevant characteristics previously described.

3.2. Agroecosystem condition variable profiles

Table 2 contains the final set of EC variables with an overview of their intrinsic and instrumental relevance and directionality as well as dataset information that support the practical applicability.

3.3. Spatial distribution of agroecosystem condition variables in Lower Saxony

Fig. 6 illustrates the spatial variation of the nine selected EC variables across Lower Saxony. Differences are notable in terms of coverage, spatial resolution, and regional patterns. Most EC variables cover the entire region of Lower Saxony, except for CR, CC and SOC, which are restricted to agricultural areas. The resolution is generally high (≤ 1 km), with coarser resolutions noticeable for SMD (5 km) and FBR (10 km).

The spatial distribution of BD and CC is relatively uniform, whereas the other EC variables reveal distinct regional patterns. The Lower Saxon hills and the Harz area in the Southeastern part of the region exhibit an

increased SOC, higher MB and SNH and lower MD, each being favorable for agroecosystem condition. A secondary, less clear cluster is observable in the region across the Weser-Aller Plains, the heathland and Elbe lowlands in the center to the East, where FBR and SNH are relatively high, and MD is mainly low.

Some EC variables contradict these trends in some parts. For example, while the South generally shows favorable values across most variables, FBR exhibits some of the lowest values in this region. Similarly, in the otherwise higher-rated centered to Eastern areas, SMD is least favorable.

3.4. Parsimony of the condition variable set

Table 3 shows the Spearman correlation coefficient between the EC variables. Correlations were predominantly negligible or weak, confirming no redundancies in the set. Exceptionally, SOC and MB exhibited a slightly higher correlation coefficient, which did not lead to the exclusion of one of the variables, given that it was still moderate (after Schober et al., 2018).

4. Discussion

We identified the most relevant agroecosystem characteristics to be considered in respective agroecosystem condition assessments globally, determined the most suitable EC variables for their description and selected the best available datasets for their spatial representation in our case study area. The discussion is structured as follows: First, we will discuss methodological aspects, focusing on some limitations of the

Table 1

Most relevant ecosystem state characteristics in croplands and/or grasslands and exemplary EC variables for their quantification. A1 Physical, A2 Chemical, B1 Compositional, B2 Structural, B3 Functional, C1 Landscape state characteristics. Characteristics marked with C are among the most relevant ones in cropland studies only, marked with G in grassland studies only, unmarked in both.

Characteristics	Condition variables (exemplary selection)
A1 Soil structure	Soil type; Soil texture; Soil depth; Potential rooting depth
Soil water regime	Water content; Water holding capacity; Hydraulic conductivity
Soil compaction (C)	Bulk density; Soil porosity
Soil stability (G)	Soil erodibility; Soil surface resistance; Aggregate stability
A2 Soil organic matter	Soil organic carbon content; Soil total carbon; Humus layer depth
Soil salinity/sodicity	Electric conductivity; Sodium adsorption ratio; Exchangeable sodium capacity
Soil nutrient status	Soil nitrogen content; Soil phosphorus content; C/N ratio
B1 Plants community	For all 3 characteristics: Total abundance; Species abundance; Family richness; Species richness; Species diversity (of different (indicator)
Invertebrates community	species (groups))
Birds community	
B2 Cropping patterns	Crop species diversity (spatial); Crop species richness (temporal); Share of permanent crops in UAA ^a
Living ground cover (G)	Intermediate crop cover; Vegetation ground cover; Canopy cover
Vertical structure (C)	Vegetation height; Height of standing deadwood; Windbreaks vertical structure
Dead plant matter (G)	Dead-to-young plants ratio; Density of snags; Crop residues; Litter cover
B3 Plant health (G)	NDVI; Plant vigor; Brix value for pastures
Microbial functionality	Microbial biomass; Microbial trophic groups richness; Metabolic quotient
C1 Presence of semi-natural elements	Density of semi-natural areas; Density of hedgerows; Buffer zone width
Landscape diversity (C)	Diversity/evenness of landscape structures; Share of other LULC ² types
Landscape fragmentation (C)	Effective mesh size; Splitting; Division; Fractal dimension

^a Utilized Agricultural Area ²Land Use Land Cover.

Table 2

Agroecosystem condition variables' profiles. The profiles provide a description of variables, dataset information and information on intrinsic and instrumental relevance and directionality. The list of ES provided under instrumental relevance does not claim to be complete (literature information was transferred to CICES V5.2 classes (Haines-Young, 2023)). Directionality information indicates whether EC improves (positive relation) or deteriorates (negative relation) with increasing variable values.

Variables' profiles		
Ecosystem condition variable: Soil bulk density (BD) [g/cm ³]		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Soil compaction
	ECT class:	Physical state (A1)
Dataset description	Name:	Soil bulk density in Europe
	Provider [Reference]:	European Soil Data Centre [ESDAC, 2024]
	Data origin:	Field data + Spatial interpolation
	Spatial resolution:	100 m
	Spatial coverage:	EU
	Temporal coverage:	2018
Variable description	Bulk density of the soil at 0–20 cm depth, interpolated from LUCAS* 2018 samples.	
Variable relevance	<p>Intrinsic relevance: The compactness of the soil determines pore space availability, essential for soil water storage and soil aeration. A reduced pore space, caused by heavy machinery use, plowing or poor crop management, impedes root growth and soil fertility by a limited water and nutrient retention. Compacted soils exhibit decreased infiltration capacity, increasing surface runoff and erosion risk, thereby restricting plant growth and enhancing water stress vulnerability (Keller et al., 2022; Indoria et al., 2020).</p> <p>Instrumental relevance: 1.1, 1.2, 2.1, 2.11, 2.12, 3.1, 3.2 (Adhikari & Hartemink, 2016; Pereira et al., 2018; Eftene et al., 2020).</p> <p>Directional meaning: negative relation.</p>	
Ecosystem condition variable: Soil moisture deficit (SMD) [-]		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Soil water regime
	ECT class:	Physical state (A1)
Dataset description	Name:	Soil moisture deficit during vegetation growing season, annual time series, 2000–2021, Aug. 2022
	Provider [Reference]:	European Environment Agency [EEA, 2022b]
	Data origin:	Remote sensing product
	Spatial resolution:	5 km
	Spatial coverage:	Europe
	Temporal coverage:	2000–2021
Variable description	Annual soil moisture anomalies in the vegetation growing season, expressed in units of Std. Dev. from the base period 1995–2019. For this study, we averaged anomalies for the period 2017–2021 to reduce the impact of inter-annual climate fluctuations.	
Variable relevance	<p>Intrinsic relevance: Soil moisture is essential for plant growth and productivity, regulating nutrient availability, salinity, aeration and temperature, and soil structure. A prolonged deficit not only impairs plant health but also reduces soil biodiversity and exacerbates soil degradation that makes it more susceptible to soil erosion (Voroney, 2019; EEA, 2021b).</p> <p>Instrumental relevance: 1.1, 1.2, 1.5, 1.9, 2.1, 2.6, 2.9, 2.10, 2.11, 2.12, 2.13, 2.14 (Adhikari & Hartemink, 2016; Ellili-Bargaoui et al., 2021).</p> <p>Directional meaning: positive relation.</p>	
Ecosystem condition variable: Changes in soil organic carbon content (SOC) [g/kg/yr]		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Soil organic matter
	ECT class:	Chemical state (A2)
Dataset description	Name:	Changes in Soil Organic Carbon in Croplands and Grasslands between 2009 and 2018

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Variables' profiles		
<i>Ecosystem condition variable: Soil bulk density (BD) [g/cm³]</i>		
Variable description	Provider [Reference]:	European Soil Data Centre [ESDAC, 2023a]
Variable relevance	Data origin:	Field data + Spatial interpolation
	Spatial resolution:	500 m
	Spatial coverage:	EU
	Temporal coverage:	2009–2018
		Changes in the SOC content at 0–20 cm depth in croplands and grasslands from 2009 to 2018.
	Intrinsic relevance:	Soil organic carbon, the main component of soil organic matter, supports nutrient cycling, enhances soil structure and stability, and increases water retention capacity (FAO 2015). Furthermore, it provides energy and habitat for soil microorganisms, which drive decomposition processes, and is crucial for carbon sequestration (Hoffland et al., 2020).
	Instrumental relevance:	1.1, 1.2, 1.5, 1.9, 2.1, 2.5, 2.6, 2.11, 2.12, 2.13, 2.14, 2.18, 2.19, 2.20, 3.1, 3.2, 3.4 (Adhikari & Hartemink, 2016; Pereira et al., 2018; Ellili-Bargaoui et al., 2021).
	Directional meaning:	positive relation.
<i>Ecosystem condition variable: Farmland bird species richness (FBR) [No./100 km²]</i>		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Bird community
	ECT class:	Compositional state (B1)
Dataset description	Name:	Population trend of bird species
	Provider [Reference]:	European Environment Agency [EEA, 2022a]
	Data origin:	Monitoring
	Spatial resolution:	10 km
	Spatial coverage:	EU
	Temporal coverage:	2013–2018
Variable description		Total number of EU common farmland bird species per 10 km grid cell, calculated from the population trends reported by the EU member states in the scope of the Birds Directive.
Variable relevance	Intrinsic relevance:	Birds are essential biodiversity components in agroecosystems, that take a high position in agricultural food webs and are sensitive towards environmental changes. Additionally, they provide crucial regulating ES (see instrumental relevance) which benefit both, the productive areas' and the adjacent environment's conditions (Donald et al., 2001; Parajuli & Ghimire, 2024).
	Instrumental relevance:	1.7, 1.10, 2.17, 2.18, 2.19, 2.21, 3.1, 3.2, 3.4 (Whelan et al., 2015; Assandri et al., 2018; Gaston, 2022; Parajuli & Ghimire, 2024).
	Directional meaning:	positive relation.
<i>Ecosystem condition variable: Crop species richness (CR) [No./km²]</i>		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Cropping patterns
	ECT class:	Structural state (B2)
Dataset description	Name:	National-scale crop type maps for Germany from combined time series of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Landsat data (2017 to 2021)
	Provider [Reference]:	Thünen Institute [Schwieder et al., 2024]
	Data origin:	Remote sensing product
	Spatial resolution:	10 m
	Spatial coverage:	Germany
	Temporal coverage:	2017–2022
Variable description		Total number of crop species in a moving window of 1 km ² around each cell. For this study, we averaged the total number for the period 2017–2021 to record the trend for a standard crop rotation period.
Variable relevance	Intrinsic relevance:	Cropping patterns are essential for agroecosystems' integrity and biodiversity. Diverse crop systems reduce pest and pathogen spread, decreasing pesticide reliance while benefiting pollinators and other beneficial organisms. Varying nutrient demands in crop rotations prevent soil depletion and enhance fertility, with nitrogen-fixing crops contributing to natural fertilization. A greater diversity of cultivation systems makes production more flexible and therefore more resilient, for instance against climate extremes (Smith et al., 2008; Gaudin et al., 2015; Renard & Tilman, 2019; He et al., 2019).
	Instrumental relevance:	1.1, 2.1, 2.5, 2.18, 2.19, 2.20 (Beillouin et al., 2021; Juventia et al., 2021).
	Directional meaning:	positive relation.
<i>Ecosystem condition variable: Share of cover crops (CC) [%/ha]</i>		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Ground cover
	ECT class:	Structural state (B2)
Dataset description	Name:	Cover Crops across Europe
	Provider [Reference]:	European Soil Data Centre [ESDAC, 2023b]
	Data origin:	Remote sensing product + Field data
	Spatial resolution:	100 m
	Spatial coverage:	EU
	Temporal coverage:	2016
Variable description		Share of CC per ha (100 m pixel) in percent during the winter season of 2016–2017. For this study, we used the provided median point estimates of the predicted CC share per pixel.
Variable relevance	Intrinsic relevance:	Cover crops provide soil protection and benefits during fallow periods and beyond. An increased soil stability by root activity decreases soil erosion risks and improves water retention. Nitrogen-fixing species and the remaining litter provide natural fertilization, while in parallel excess nutrients are absorbed and nitrogen leaching is prevented. The improved soil conditions support increased soil microbial diversity and activity, while the aboveground biomass provides habitat that supports an increased biodiversity at agroecosystem level. Additionally, root exudates can support weed, insect and diseases management (Thapa et al., 2018; Quintarelli et al., 2022).
	Instrumental relevance:	1.1, 1.2, 2.1, 2.5, 2.6, 2.18, 2.20, 2.21 (Schipanski, 2014; Juventia et al., 2021).
	Directional meaning:	positive relation.
<i>Ecosystem condition variable: Soil microbial biomass (MB) [μg C_{mic}/g soil dry weight]</i>		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Microbial functionality
	ECT class:	Functional state (B3)

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

<i>Variables' profiles</i>		
<i>Ecosystem condition variable: Soil bulk density (BD) [g/cm³]</i>		
Dataset description	Name:	Soil microbial biomass & respiration
	Provider [Reference]:	European Soil Data Centre [ESDAC, 2021]
	Data origin:	Field data + Spatial interpolation
	Spatial resolution:	1 km
	Spatial coverage:	EU
	Temporal coverage:	2018
Variable description	Potential soil microbial (bacterial and fungal) biomass, predicted from LUCAS* 2018 samples. For this study, we used the dataset that considered the land-cover type for the prediction.	
Variable relevance	Intrinsic relevance: Microbial soil organisms drive decomposition and turnover of organic matter in soils, and thereby underpin key functions such as carbon and nutrient cycling as well as carbon sequestration, soil stabilization, water cycling, breakdown of contaminants and suppression of diseases in the soil (Stockdale & Murphy, 2017). Instrumental relevance: 1.1, 1.5, 1.8, 1.10, 2.1, 2.5, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10 2.17, 2.18, 2.19, 2.20, 2.21 (Aislabie & Deslippe, 2013; Adhikari & Hartemink, 2016; Saccá et al., 2017). Directional meaning: positive relation.	
<i>Ecosystem condition variable: Density of (semi-)natural habitats (SNH) [%/km²]</i>		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Presence of semi-natural elements
	ECT class:	Landscape state (C1)
Dataset 1 description	Name:	High Resolution Small Woody Features
	Provider [Reference]:	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service [EEA, 2023]
	Data origin:	Remote sensing product
	Spatial resolution:	5 m
	Spatial coverage:	Europe
	Temporal coverage:	2017–2019
Dataset 2 description	Name:	CLCplus Backbone 2021 (raster 10 m), Europe, 3-yearly
	Provider [Reference]:	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service [EEA, 2024]
	Data origin:	Remote sensing product
	Spatial resolution:	10 m
	Spatial coverage:	Europe
	Temporal coverage:	2020–2022
Variable description	Percentage of cells assigned to (semi-) natural land use types (CLCplus Backbone 'forest' classes) or woody landscape features (CLCplus Backbone class 'low growing woody plants', SWF) in a moving window of 1 km ² around each cell.	
Variable relevance	Intrinsic relevance: (Semi-)natural habitats in agroecosystems describe communities of non-crop plant species in or outside of the crop, altered by human activities but with mainly intact ecological processes. Including, for instance, woody structures, hedgerows, field margins, riparian stripes or fallow land, they provide foraging grounds, breeding or overwintering sites and wildlife corridors that support biodiversity. Additionally, as permanent structures, they can protect soils and regulate fluxes of nutrients and water (Hietala-Koivu et al., 2004; Benton et al., 2003; Holland et al., 2017; Holden et al., 2019; Tarjuelo et al., 2020; Hertzog et al., 2023; European Commission, 2021). Instrumental relevance: 2.1, 2.3, 2.5 2.6, 2.9, 2.10, 2.11, 2.12, 2.17, 2.18, 2.19, 2.20 (García-Feced et al., 2015; Assandri et al., 2018; Olimpí et al. 2022; Rosenfield et al., 2022; Lange et al., 2023). Directional meaning: positive relation.	
<i>Ecosystem condition variable: Effective mesh density (MD) [No./1000 km²]</i>		
Variable context	Characteristic:	Landscape fragmentation
	ECT class:	Landscape state (C1)
Dataset description	Name:	Landscape fragmentation Effective Mesh Density time series
	Provider [Reference]:	European Environment Agency [EEA, 2021a]
	Data origin:	Remote sensing product + Field data
	Spatial resolution:	100 m
	Spatial coverage:	Europe
	Temporal coverage:	2017–2019
Variable description	Number of meshes (fragmenting geometries such as impervious surfaces and traffic infrastructure that hinder movement between different parts of the landscape) per 1000 km ² .	
Variable relevance	Intrinsic relevance: Landscape fragmentation by artificial barriers such as industrial sites, roads and railways, is one of the major threats to species in industrialized countries. They isolate habitats and hamper species movement, and are often sources of pollutants, noise or light that disturb sensitive species. Important species affected in agroecosystems are for instance pollinator insects, soil arthropods, and birds whose absence leads to the loss of important ecological functions and ES (Jaeger, 2000; Bailey et al., 2010; Montoya et al., 2021; Markfeld et al., 2022). Instrumental relevance: 1.1, 2.1, 2.5, 2.20 (Wei et al., 2020; Mirghaed & Souri, 2022). Directional meaning: negative relation.	

*Land Use/Land Cover Area Frame Survey.

Data origin: categories are harmonized, for detailed description please visit dataset provider.

Spatial coverage: categories are harmonized and coverages can slightly differ between datasets and years. For detailed description please visit dataset provider.

Instrumental relevance: 1.1 Crop provisioning services, 1.2 Grazed biomass provisioning services, 1.5 Wood provisioning services, 1.7 Wild animals, plant and other provisioning services, 1.8 Genetic material services, 1.9 Water supply, 1.10 Other provisioning services, 2.1 Global climate regulation services, 2.5 Soil quality regulation services, 2.6 Soil erosion control services, 2.8 Solid waste remediation, 2.9&2.10 Water purification services, 2.11&2.12 Water flow regulation services, 2.13&2.14 Flood mitigation services, 2.17 Pollination services, 2.18 Pest control services, 2.19 Disease control services, 2.20 Nursery population and habitat maintenance services, 2.21 Other regulating and maintenance services, 3.1 Recreation related services, 3.1 Recreation-related services, 3.2 Visual amenity services, 3.4 Spiritual, artistic and symbolic services.

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of the nine selected EC variables across the case study area Lower Saxony. Based on (a) ESDAC, 2024 (b) EEA, 2022b (c) ESDAC, 2023a (d) EEA, 2022a (e) Schwieder et al., 2024 (f) ESDAC, 2023b (g) ESDAC, 2021 (h) EEA, 2023 & EEA, 2024 (i) EEA, 2021a. For more detailed variables and datasets descriptions see Table 2.

SEEA EA guidelines and the developed selection process. Second, we will examine the results concerning the most relevant characteristics and the most suitable EC variables, particularly in the context of transferability and comparability. Finally, we will outline potential future steps that could build on the study's results.

4.1. Framework strength and limitations

The SEEA EA framework (UN et al., 2024) provides extensive definitions, rules and recommendations for EC assessments, which formed the primary basis for this study. The structuring of an EC assessment into consecutive stages seems well-developed and offers a meaningful chronological order of assessment steps, while the ECT supports a

classification that ensures a comprehensive consideration of abiotic, biotic and landscape characteristics. However, some uncertainties remain that need to be further addressed and clarified.

4.1.1. Classification of characteristics and condition variables

Identifying relevant characteristics for EC assessments requires an explicit understanding of what components are covered by the respective ECT classes and what detail of information is necessary. Relevant ecosystem characteristics and EC variables can, however, appear in a nested structure, leading to overlaps where differentiation is hindered when similar descriptors are used (UN et al., 2024). For example, while aboveground vegetation can be considered a structural characteristic described by the variable 'Vegetation density [t/ha], vegetation density

Table 3

Strength of correlation* between the selected agroecosystem condition variables. BD = Bulk Density, SMD=Soil Moisture Deficit, SOC = changes in Soil Organic Carbon content, FBR = Farmland Bird species Richness, CR=Crop species Richness, CC = share of Cover Crops, MB = Microbial Biomass, SNH = density of Semi-Natural Habitats, MD = Mesh Density.

	BD	SMD	SOC	FBR	CR	CC	MB	SNH	MD
BD	1								
SMD	-0.048	1							
SOC	0.245	0.089	1						
FBR	0.120	-0.105	0.001	1					
CR	0.173	-0.146	0.191	0.123	1				
CC	0.010	-0.012	-0.134	0.007	-0.059	1			
MB	0.148	0.306	0.504	-0.147	0.125	-0.198	1		
SNH	-0.224	-0.273	-0.255	-0.001	-0.078	0.027	-0.352	1	
MD	0.065	0.049	0.087	-0.068	0.106	0.002	0.105	-0.084	1

*Negligible correlation 0 – 0.1, Weak correlation 0.11–0.39, Moderate correlation 0.4 – 0.69, Strong correlation 0.7 – 0.89, Very strong correlation 0.9 – 1.00 (after Schober et al., 2018).

itself can also be viewed as a more specific structural characteristic, quantified by the variable 'Leaf Area Index [-]'. This not only introduces uncertainties within one ECT class, but also across different ECT classes. For instance, biomass can be interpreted as the main structural characteristic. However, when expressed as growth in [t/year], biomass can also describe the functional characteristic of ecosystem productivity. Although flexibility is intended in the framework, inaccurate implementation can lead to weak indicator-indicandum relationships, threatening the validity of the indicator (Heink & Kowarik, 2010a), and can complicate the already ambiguous assignment of some EC variables to ECT classes (Czúcz et al., 2021a; Vallecillo et al., 2022).

Refining the ECT classification within a hierarchical structure could facilitate differentiation and enhance the proper selection of EC variables (Maes et al., 2020). In this study, we applied a thematic interpretive synthesis (Thomas & Harden, 2008), systematically grouping related and overlapping EC variables through iterative refinement to highlight meaningful sub-characteristics.

4.1.1.1. Interpretive synthesis for ECT refinement. Multiple iterative cycles were required to adapt to the emerging patterns in the variables. Most adjustments involved creating new sub-characteristics and reassigning variables, and occasionally, characteristics names were refined to ensure exclusivity (e.g. the former characteristic 'vegetation biomass' was renamed to 'living vegetation biomass' to make the distinction from litter biomass clear). Exceptionally, reassignment of variables across ECT classes was also necessary. For example, all litter-related variables were initially classified as structural, following SEEA EA guidelines (UN et al., 2024), but the specific variables 'litter type' and 'litter movement' were later reassigned to functional characteristics as the sub-characteristic of 'decomposition processes' emerged. This case highlights the issue of assigning variables to ECT classes independently of their characteristic (the indicandum). The problem can be illustrated by the example NDWI, suggested as a physical variable in the SEEA EA (UN et al., 2024), but often used to assess plant health, a rather functional characteristic (e.g. in Maes et al., 2023). From this finding we can conclude that indicator lists to be recommended in the future must always be considered together with the characteristics. While the extracting of single variables during the literature review and their initial classification into ECT classes was the most straightforward method for our study, the associated decoupling from the larger study context carries a risk of misinterpretation (Thomas & Harden, 2008).

Our interpretive approach worked particularly well for physical and chemical characteristics, where there are many well-established metrics with a clear common understanding of what they indicate. Such clear indicator-indicandum relationships (Heink & Kowarik, 2010b) greatly facilitated the alignment of variables and characteristics. In contrast, the groupings were less clear for structural and functional characteristics, partly due to lacking or unclear units and descriptors (e.g. % for both vegetation cover and density) and partly caused by descriptors

connected to multiple possible characteristics (e.g. 'height of standing deadwood' describing both vertical structure and dead plant matter), which potentially introduced interpretation bias. Grouping of plant compositional characteristics proved to be exceptionally challenging, due to a large variety of applied variables (taxonomic groups, guilds and functional groups, species origins (native vs. alien), ecological status ('threatened' etc.) and metrics (diversity, richness, abundance, presence etc.). To avoid overinterpretation, here we decided to remain with the broad taxonomy-based classes. However, in the future, compositional characteristics should be explicitly addressed and refined, preferably with a focus on functional groups (Moonen & Bärberi, 2008). Some initial ideas for classification turned out to be unsuitable, like the distinction of productive and semi-natural areas to acknowledge the special character of agroecosystems. Though feasible for some structural and landscape state characteristics (e.g., cropping patterns on the productive land, vertical structure of semi-natural features), it was hindered by overlaps in other aspects (e.g. 'ground cover' both by crops and semi-natural features).

4.1.1.2. Considerations for the application of the refined ECT. The different aspects and challenges of the grouping have led to varying levels of detail and a limited comparability across ECT classes. However, this is not necessarily a weakness, given that the six ECT classes inherently represent distinct characteristics that cannot be directly compared. As for the ECT classes, overlaps and borderline cases remain in the sub-characteristics, but are not problematic as long as one solution is used consistently (Czúcz et al., 2021a).

The identification of more specific characteristics can support the selection of individual suitable variables, as demonstrated in this study. Additionally, a refined ECT classification could facilitate the compilation of more comprehensive variable sets. While SEEA EA requires a minimum of one variable per ECT class (United Nations, European Union, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, International Monetary Fund, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank, 2024), such a simplification does not accurately reflect reality. With the introduction of additional levels, this minimum requirement could be extended to encompass more specific characteristics. In this study, we limited the selection process to the three most frequently used characteristics, primarily for practical reasons. However, it could be expanded to encompass all 39 characteristics, potentially resulting in a more comprehensive set of variables to describe the EC (Czúcz et al., 2021a). Finally, a refined classification of ecosystem characteristics may support the selection of suitable sets of variables for different spatial assessment scales, where a more detailed distinction is especially relevant at smaller scales with higher resolutions.

4.1.2. Applicability of suitability criteria

The SEEA EA selection criteria set the principles for selecting variables for EC assessments, while allowing for a flexible order of application and leaving room for interpretation to suit the specific assessment objectives (Czúcz et al., 2021b; United Nations, European Union, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, International Monetary Fund, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank, 2024). Different interpretations, however, can impact the selection and lead to different outcomes. To our knowledge, there is no study so far that dealt with the criteria in detail and defined them for a specific assessment purpose. This study is a first attempt to apply and specify the criteria, on which further assessments can build.

The distinction between the stricter ‘enabling criteria’ and the softer ‘quality criteria’ ensures SEEA EA-alignment while allowing for adaptation to data availability. However, within this classification, the specific requirements for each criterion have an influence on the selection process and the results, which was for instance evident for the criteria *validity* and *reliability* in this study. We defined spatial explicitness as an issue of *validity*, leading to the exclusion of spatially aggregated variables. However, other studies do not necessarily argue against spatially aggregated data (Vallecillo et al., 2022), so spatial explicitness could have also been defined as an aspect of *reliability*, allowing to keep such data when alternatives are lacking. The same applies to the spatial resolution, which can be limited both under *availability* and *reliability* aspects. By setting the criteria rather strictly, we opted for a smaller set of suitable EC variables instead of a larger, but potentially more inaccurate set.

We determined the order of criteria during the exclusion process in a way that minimized the necessary research effort and adapted it to the current situation where concrete practical knowledge is still incomplete. Therefore, the criteria of instrumental relevance and directional meaning were applied last. As respective knowledge is growing, in the future, these criteria can potentially be verified at an earlier stage, leaving only practical criteria for verification.

4.2. Relevant agroecosystem characteristics

The most often applied characteristics in cropland studies globally were (in descending order): Soil nutrient status, Cropping patterns, Soil structure and Microbial functionality. In grassland studies they were: Plant community characteristics, Soil nutrient status, Soil structure and Ground cover. The results were relatively clear and can contribute to compiling a list of universally relevant agroecosystem characteristics, as called for by Czúcz et al. (2021b) for instance. What is important to notice is that, even though generally important, Soil structure is conceptually unsuitable to derive EC variables due to lacking sufficiently clear sensitivity to human impacts. Also, some missing characteristics have to be discussed.

For both agricultural land use types, a tendency towards soil-related characteristics can be observed, which is undermined by the fact that both ECT classes of physical and chemical characteristics are almost entirely limited to soil characteristics. Studies have only occasionally addressed physical characteristics of the air (e.g. vapour pressure and temperature, Bakhralinova et al., 2016; Bray et al., 2016) or (ground-) water (Hess et al., 2000; Wang et al., 2009), but these were either excluded for being unsuitable (e.g. climate variables are rather to be considered as Drivers of change) or not relevant due to low frequency. Chemical characteristics like water or air pollution are almost completely disregarded, albeit their evident negative effects on agroecosystem condition and functioning (Plutino et al., 2022; Khan & Bhatt, 2023). Regarding water characteristics, this may be explained by the issue of different classifications of agroecosystems. Even though some definitions consider landscape features like ponds and ditches as integral parts of agroecosystems (Vallecillo et al., 2022), studies rarely include their condition as a sub-indicator. Instead, studies on freshwater EC in

agricultural landscapes are usually limited to the actual water body (e.g. Williams et al., 2020), indicating that the systems tend to be assessed separately.

The strong focus on soils, which is the most important natural resource for agricultural production (Blumetto et al., 2019), may lead to the conclusion that productivity is still the main driver behind condition assessments, especially in croplands. The distribution is different among grassland studies, even though soil nutrient status and structure are still among the most important characteristics. The frequent use of plant community characteristics is outstanding, and most likely stems from the increased interest in grassland ecosystems as biodiversity hotspots (Zhao, 2023). But also other vegetation characteristics like dead plant matter and vertical structure were considered more often, pointing to a more general view on EC in grassland assessments.

4.3. Key agroecosystem condition variables applicability and transferability

The nine selected EC variables can be used as a foundational base for agroecosystem condition assessments, comprehensively and reliably covering all of the six relevant state characteristics with at least one variable. The selection process was designed to make the final set transferable and applicable for other studies, both in spatial terms and context-wise. The literature review included studies from various types of agroecosystems across different regions. This broad basis allowed for the identification of the core characteristics of agroecosystems, independent from specific features of single studied ecosystems. Furthermore, EC variables were selected in a transparent process based on objective selection criteria, rather than for a specific assessment purpose or policy, allowing for a broad application.

The datasets mainly cover the entire European area, allowing for application in any other European study region. The only exception are the datasets for CR, which were limited to Germany. They were preferred due to better temporal coverage (*reliability* before *comparability*) but can be replaced by another highly resolved European dataset (European Commission, 2022).

Notably, the final set exhibits a number of overlaps with indicators suggested in the established MAES framework (Maes et al., 2018), the SEEA EA (United Nations, European Union, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, International Monetary Fund, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank, 2024) and the recent SEEA EA-aligned EU-wide methodology to map and assess EC (Vallecillo et al., 2022). The EC variables SOC, FBR, and SNH are consistently included across all three frameworks, with only slight variations in descriptors or units. For five additional EC variables (BD, SMD, CR, MB, MD), at least one other framework shows overlaps, with partly differing EC variables that nevertheless describe the same characteristic. Only the variable CC, reflecting the characteristics of vegetation cover, was unique to this study. The significance of overlaps of the selected EC variables across frameworks points to the robustness of the developed selection process and confirms the applicability of the selected variables.

4.4. Applications

Based on the application of the EC variables, initial conclusions on the condition of Lower Saxony’s agroecosystem can be drawn. The clustering of favorable variable values in the southern Lower Saxon Hills, as well as in the region across Weser-Aller Plains, Heathland and Elbe lowlands in the center to east, suggest a better EC compared to the western regions. This appears plausible, considering the overall less intensive agriculture in hilly areas and heathlands. Some relationships between EC variables allow further interpretation; for instance, the higher density of SNH and lower MD in the center to east promote a higher biodiversity and may explain the tendency towards higher FBR. However, due to their partly contradictory statements, a separate

consideration of the EC variables does not allow statements on the overall agroecosystem condition yet. Nevertheless, the current set can be applied for different purposes.

The compiled set of EC variables covers the main aspects of agroecosystem condition and is thus relevant for policy- and decision-making. Their directional meaning allows for the monitoring and reporting of trends in certain EC components – whether improving or deteriorating – which can be a sufficient base for statements in certain contexts (UN et al. 2024). For instance, the EU's Nature Restoration Law demands for an 'increasing trend' of selected indicators (European Commission, 2024). As a planning tool, the EC variables allow for region-specific recommendations: in Lower Saxony, for instance, the presumed higher biodiversity in the center to east likely reduces the need for habitat connectivity measures, whereas the increased soil moisture deficit must be addressed through appropriate soil protection measures. When used for regional planning or management, it should be noted that the variables merely reflect the common relevant agroecosystem characteristics. Characteristics of particular regional agroecosystems – e.g. in the heath and peatlands of the Lower Saxony example case – were not in the focus of this study and were therefore not considered during the selection. For an adapted assessment, the minimum set should be complemented by regional characteristics, which could be defined for instance through a focused literature review or expert evaluation.

The variables can also serve as input data for process-based modeling, as demonstrated by Hinsch et al. (2024), where a non-rescaled EC indicator was used to differentiate best, medium, and worst EC scenarios for pollination ES capacities. Including the EC in ES assessments allows for more differentiated statements compared to assessments based on Land Use/Land Cover types only (ibid.). For the purpose of ES model implication, the set potentially has to be adapted thematically and in terms of suitability for different spatial scales by removing or complementing EC variables.

5. Conclusions

This study is the first – to our knowledge – to define agroecosystem characteristics within the SEEA EA ECT and apply the selection criteria for EC indicators in a structured process for a transparent agroecosystem condition variable selection, that can be built upon. We propose that the selected variables serve as key variables for agroecosystem condition assessments in Europe on regional scales. Applied altogether, they constitute a minimum set that ensures as much as possible comprehensiveness of assessments while maintaining parsimony and practicality. The transparency of the selection process also allows for future adaptation of the variable set, for instance in an updated data inventory as data availability increases. However, several limitations remain that should be addressed to enhance the transferability and robustness of the approach and results.

The development of sub-characteristics through interpretive synthesis relies on the specific 'sample' of variables, limiting the transferability to other contexts. The bias could be reduced by expanding or cross-validating the variable set, e.g., through a broader literature review. Comparing different methods and the resulting subclasses could support a more reliable definition of relevant agroecosystem sub-characteristics. Additionally, separate syntheses for cropland and grassland studies may result in different subclasses that potentially better reflect the sub-ecosystem's characteristics. While the subclasses at a fine level need to be ecosystem-type specific to avoid information loss, an improved classification should aim for broad applicability across ecosystem types and biomes. To strike a balance between universality and specificity, additional intermediate levels could be introduced (Czúcz et al., 2021a; Czúcz et al., 2021b).

Regarding the selection criteria, two criteria require further investigation. First, in this study *instrumental relevance*, the relevance of an EC variable for ES supply, was only partially verified through a non-

systematic literature search, holding the risk of misinterpretation. A systematic analysis of the complex interrelations between EC and ES indicators is needed to address fragmentation and synthesize existing knowledge effectively. Testing selected EC variables in ES models (using different combinations, different weightings etc., Nardo et al., 2005) could provide further insights.

Secondly, the *comparability* of the selected EC variables across ecosystem types was only marginally addressed, as this study focused solely on agroecosystems. Future research should examine how these variables align with key EC variables for other ecosystem types, refining a standardized minimum set. For instance, FBR has a large potential for comparability, as it is recommended as EC variable for all terrestrial as well as freshwater and marine ecosystems (Maes et al., 2018; Vallecillo et al., 2022) and has already been applied in SEEA EA forest condition accounts (Maes et al., 2023). Similarly, BD, SOC, density of SNH, and MD have been suggested for various terrestrial ecosystem types and should be further examined as potential key variables (Maes et al., 2018; Vallecillo et al., 2022). However, certain variables, such as CR and CC remain highly ecosystem-specific and may not be directly comparable.

Finally, while applicable for descriptive purposes and as model input data, the variables are not suitable for stand-alone normative interpretation ('good' or 'bad') of the condition, due to a lack of proper rescaling. To allow for this, future work to define reference levels will be essential. Here, the determination of adapted reference levels, considering regional climate, soil or vegetation, increases the regional informative value of the commonly applicable variables.

By addressing the discussed limitations, the selection process for EC variables can be further improved and the variables can be developed into robust tools for integrated ecosystem assessments, fostering alignment with international frameworks and enhancing their relevance for decision-making and sustainable agroecosystem management.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used OpenAI Chat GPT in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Emily Bank: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Sabine Lange:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Bálint Czúcz:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Malte Hinsch:** Writing – review & editing. **Benjamin Burkhard:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the European Union under grant agreement No. 101060415, SELINA (Science for Evidence-based and sustainable decisions about NATural capital). We thank Prof Claas Nendel (ZALF Müncheberg) for providing early access to the crop type data used to calculate Crop species richness prior to its publication. We furthermore want to thank Angie Faust (Leibniz University Hannover) for an English language check.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2025.113813>.

Data availability

The data produced in this study are accessible in the Zenodo data repository. The underlying original data must be requested from the respective institutions.

References

- Adhikari, K., Hartemink, A.E., 2016. Linking soils to ecosystem services — a global review. *Geoderma* 262, 101–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.08.009>.
- Aislabie, J., Deslippe, J.R., 2013. Soil microbes and their contribution to soil services. In: Dymond, J.R. (Ed.), *Ecosystem Services in New Zealand - Conditions and Trends*. Manaaki Whenua Press New Zealand, pp. 143–161.
- Assandri, G., Bogliani, G., Pedrini, P., Brambilla, M., 2018. Beautiful agricultural landscapes promote cultural ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation. *Agr Ecosyst Environ* 256, 200–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.01.012>.
- Bailey, D., Schmidt-Entling, M.H., Eberhart, P., Herrmann, J.D., Hofer, G., Kormann, U., Herzog, F., 2010. Effects of habitat amount and isolation on biodiversity in fragmented traditional orchards. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 47 (5), 1003–1013. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2010.01858.x>.
- Bakhralina, A.S., Kurishbayev, A.K., Serepkaev, N.A., Stybayev, G.Z., Nogayev, A.A., 2016. Condition of Pastures Neighboring to the villages in Enbekshilder District of Akmola Region and the Effectiveness of some Surface Improvement Techniques. *Biosci. Biotechnol. Res. Asia* 13 (2), 733–742. <https://doi.org/10.13005/bbra/2092>.
- Bedolla-Rivera, H.I., La Xochilt Negrete-Rodríguez, M., d. L., Del Medina-Herrera, M. R., Gámez-Vázquez, F. P., Álvarez-Bernal, D., Samaniego-Hernández, M., Conde-Barajas, A., 2020. Development of a Soil Quality Index for Soils under Different Agricultural Management Conditions in the Central Lowlands of Mexico: Physicochemical, Biological and Ecophysiological Indicators. *Sustainability* 12 (22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12229754>.
- Beillouin, D., Ben-Ari, T., Malézieux, E., Seufert, V., Makowski, D., 2021. Positive but variable effects of crop diversification on biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 27 (19), 4697–4710. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15747>.
- Benton, T.G., Vickery, J.A., Wilson, J.D., 2003. Farmland biodiversity: is habitat heterogeneity the key? *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 18 (4), 182–188. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(03\)00011-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(03)00011-9).
- Bhattacharjee, A., 2012. *Social Science Research: Principles, Methods, and Practices* (Second edition). *Textbooks Collection: Vol. 3*. Tampa, Florida. Retrieved from https://digitalcommons.usf.edu/oa_textbooks/3.
- Blickensdorfer, L., Schwieder, M., Pflugmacher, D., Nendel, C., Erasmí, S., Hostert, P., 2022. Mapping of crop types and crop sequences with combined time series of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Landsat 8 data for Germany. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 269, 112831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112831>.
- Blumetto, O., Castagna, A., Cardozo, G., García, F., Tiscornia, G., Ruggia, A., Albin, A., 2019. Ecosystem Integrity Index, an innovative environmental evaluation tool for agricultural production systems. *Ecol. Ind.* 101, 725–733. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.01.077>.
- Bray, S.G., Allen, D.E., Harms, B.P., Reid, D.J., Fraser, G.W., Dalal, R.C., Gunther, R., 2016. Is land condition a useful indicator of soil organic carbon stock in Australia's northern grazing land? *The Rangeland Journal* 38 (3), 229–243. <https://doi.org/10.1071/RJ15097>.
- Burgass, M.J., Halpern, B.S., Nicholson, E., Milner-Gulland, E.J., 2017. Navigating uncertainty in environmental composite indicators. *Ecol. Ind.* 75, 268–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.12.034>.
- Condé, S., Richard, D., Liamine, N., & Leclère, A.-S. (2002). *Europeas Biodiversity - biogeographical regions and seas: Biogeographical regions in Europe* (EEA Report No. 1/2002).
- Crossman, N.D., 2017. Data and quantification issues. In: Burkhard, B., Maes, J. (Eds.), *Mapping Ecosystem Services*. Pensoft Publishers, Sofia, pp. 267–272.
- Czúcz, B., Keith, H., Driver, A., Jackson, B., Nicholson, E., Maes, J., 2021. A common typology for ecosystem characteristics and ecosystem condition variables. *One Ecosyst.* 6. <https://doi.org/10.3897/oneco.6.e58218>.
- Czúcz, B., Keith, H., Maes, J., Driver, A., Jackson, B., Nicholson, E., Obst, C., 2021. Selection criteria for ecosystem condition indicators. *Ecol. Ind.* 133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108376>.
- Destatis, 2024. Bodenfläche nach Nutzungsarten und Bundesländern. <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Branchen-Unternehmen/Landwirtschaft-Forstwirtschaft-Fischerei/Flaechennutzung/Tabellen/bodenflaeche-laender.html>.
- Dixon-Woods, M., Cavers, D., Agarwal, S., Annandale, E., Arthur, A., Harvey, J., Sutton, A.J., 2006. Conducting a critical interpretive synthesis of the literature on access to healthcare by vulnerable groups. *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 6, 35. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-6-35>.
- Donald, P.F., Green, R.E., Heath, M.F., 2001. Agricultural intensification and the collapse of Europe's farmland bird populations. *Proceedings in the Royal Society Biological Sciences* 268 (1462), 25–29. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2000.1325>.
- Edens, B., Maes, J., Hein, L., Obst, C., Siikamäki, J., Schenau, S., Alferi, A., 2022. Establishing the SEEA Ecosystem Accounting as a global standard. *Ecosystem Services* 54, 101413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101413>.
- Eftene, A., Ignat, P., Chiurciu, I.-A., Manea, A., Raducu, D., Dumitru, S., 2020. Soil bulk density as important management factor and ecosystem services well function. *Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development* 20 (4), 175–184.
- Ellili-Bargaoui, Y., Walter, C., Lemerrier, B., Michot, D., 2021. Assessment of six soil ecosystem services by coupling simulation modelling and field measurement of soil properties. *Ecological Indicators* 121, 107211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.107211>.
- European Commission, 2022. EUCROPMAP 2022. <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datas-et/555e5d1d-1aae-4320-a716-2e6d18aa1e7c>.
- European Commission, 2020. *Communication from the Commission to the European parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions. EU biodiversity strategy for 2030: Bringing nature back into our lives*. Brussels.
- European Commission, 2021. Semi-natural habitats: Glossary item. <https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/glossary-item/semi-natural-habitats-en>.
- European Environmental Agency (EEA), 2021a. Landscape fragmentation Effective Mesh Density 2018: major and medium anthropogenic fragmenting elements (FGA2-S), Dec. 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/databub/databubitem-view/9d0b51f9-047d-4af1-89eb-3756e46ffc53?activeAccordion=>.
- European Environmental Agency (EEA), 2021. Soil moisture deficit. Retrieved from. <http://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/soil-moisture-deficit>.
- European Environmental Agency (EEA), 2022. Population trend of bird species: datasets from Article 12, Birds Directive 2009/147/EC reporting (2013–2018) - PUBLIC VERSION - Apr. 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/databub/databubitem-view/96e1b9b1-ee94-4547-ad61-8059df7240bf?activeAccordion=>.
- European Environmental Agency (EEA), 2022b. Soil moisture deficit during the vegetation growing season, annual time-series, 2000–2021, Aug. 2022. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/databub/databubitem-view/b85129e3-d53e-4d06-943d-c9fa3bf5391f?activeAccordion=>.
- European Environmental Agency (EEA), 2024. CLCplus Backbone 2021 (raster 10 m), Europe, 3-yearly, Jun. 2024. Retrieved from <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/clc-backbone/clc-backbone-2021>.
- European Environmental Agency (EEA), 2023. Small Woody Features 2018 (raster 5m), Europe, 3-yearly, May 2023.. Retrieved from. <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-small-woody-features/small-woody-features-2018>.
- European Commission, 2024. Regulation 2024/1991 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2024 on nature restoration and amending Regulation (EU) 2022/869. *Nature Restoration Law, Official Journal of the European Union*.
- European Soil Data Center, 2023. Changes in Soil Organic Carbon in Croplands and Grasslands between 2009 and 2018. Retrieved from. <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/SOC-changes-2009-18>.
- European Soil Data Center, 2023. Cover Crops across Europe. Retrieved from. <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/cover-crops-across-europe>.
- European Soil Data Center (ESDAC), 2024. Soil Bulk Density in Europe.. Retrieved from. <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-bulk-density-europe>.
- European Soil Data Center (ESDAC), 2021. Soil microbial biomass and respiration.. Retrieved from. <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-microbial-biomass-and-respiration>.
- Farrell, C., Coleman, L., Kelly-Quinn, M., Obst, C.G., Eigenraam, M., Norton, D., Stout, J., 2021. Applying the System of Environmental Economic Accounting-Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA-EA) framework at catchment scale to develop ecosystem extent and condition accounts. *One Ecosystem* 6, e65582. <https://doi.org/10.3897/oneco.6.e65582>.
- Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, 2021. *Land use statistics and indicators. Global, regional and country trends 1990-2019*. (FAOSTAT Analytical Brief Series No 28).
- Gabrielsen, P., & Bosch, P., 2003. *Environmental Indicators: Typology and Use in Reporting* (EEA internal working paper).
- García-Feced, C., Weissteiner, C.J., Baraldi, A., Paracchini, M.L., Maes, J., Zulian, G., Pérez-Soba, M., 2015. Semi-natural vegetation in agricultural land: European map and links to ecosystem service supply. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 35 (1), 273–283. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-014-0238-1>.
- Gaston, K.J., 2022. Birds and ecosystem services. *Current Biology* 32 (20), R1163–R1166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2022.07.053>.
- Gaudin, A.C.M., Tolhurst, T.N., Ker, A.P., Janovicek, K., Tortora, C., Martin, R.C., Deen, W., 2015. Increasing crop diversity mitigates weather variations and improves yield stability. *PLoS ONE* 10 (2). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0113261>.
- Gedoz, M., Freitas, E.M., Da Silva, V.L., Johann, L., 2021. Edaphic Invertebrates as Indicators of Soil Integrity Quality. *Floresta E Ambiente* 28 (2). <https://doi.org/10.1590/2179-8087-floram-2020-0069>.
- Granata, E., Pedrini, P., Marchesi, L., Fedrigotti, C., Biella, P., Ronchi, S., Brambilla, M., 2023. Environmental and management factors drive biological communities and ecosystem services in agroecosystems along an urban-natural gradient. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 357, 108693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108693>.
- Haines-Young, R., 2023. *Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) V5.2 Guidance on the Application of the Revised Structure*. Retrieved from: www.cices.eu.
- Hämäläinen, R.P., Alaja, S., 2008. The threat of weighting biases in environmental decision analysis. *Ecological Economics* 68 (1–2), 556–569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2008.05.025>.

- He, H., Liu, L., Munir, S., Bashir, N.H., Wang, Y., Yang, J., Li, C., 2019. Crop diversity and pest management in sustainable agriculture. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture* 18 (9), 1945–1952. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119\(19\)62689-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119(19)62689-4).
- Heink, U., Kowarik, I., 2010. What are indicators? on the definition of indicators in ecology and environmental planning. *Ecological Indicators* 10 (3), 584–593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2009.09.009>.
- Heink, U., Kowarik, I., 2010. What criteria should be used to select biodiversity indicators? *Biodiversity and Conservation* 19 (13), 3769–3797. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-010-9926-6>.
- Hertzog, L.R., Klimek, S., Röder, N., Frank, C., Böhner, H.G.S., Kamp, J., 2023. Associations between farmland birds and fallow area at large scales: consistently positive over three periods of the EU Common Agricultural Policy but moderated by landscape complexity. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 60 (6), 1077–1088. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14400>.
- Hess, G.R., Campbell, C.L., Fiscus, D.A., Hellkamp, A.S., McQuaid, B.F., Munster, M.J., Shafer, S.R., 2000. A Conceptual Model and Indicators for Assessing the Ecological Condition of Agricultural Lands. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 29 (3), 728–737. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2000.00472425002900030007x>.
- Heunisch, C., Caspers, G., Elbracht, J., Röhling, H.-G., Schwarz, C., Streif, H., 2017. Erdgeschichte Von Niedersachsen Geologie Und Landschaftsentwicklung (GeoBerichte No. 6), Hannover. https://doi.org/10.48476/geober_6_2017.
- Hietala-Koivu, R., Järvenpää, T., Helenius, J., 2004. Value of semi-natural areas as biodiversity indicators in agricultural landscapes. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 101 (1), 9–19. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809\(03\)00273-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(03)00273-1).
- Hinsch, M., Zuilian, G., Stekker, S., Rega, C., Nabuurs, G.-J., Verweij, P., Burkhard, B., 2024. Assessing pollinator habitat suitability considering ecosystem condition in the Hannover Region, Germany. *Landscape Ecology* 39 (47). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-024-01851-x>.
- Hoffland, E., Kuyper, T.W., Comans, R.N.J., Creamer, R.E., 2020. Eco-functionality of organic matter in soils. *Plant and Soil* 455 (1–2), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s1104-020-04651-9>.
- Holden, J., Grayson, R.P., Berdeni, D., Bird, S., Chapman, P.J., Edmondson, J.L., Leake, J. R., 2019. The role of hedgerows in soil functioning within agricultural landscapes. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 273, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2018.11.027>.
- Holland, J.M., Douma, J.C., Crowley, L., James, L., Kor, L., Stevenson, D.R., Smith, B.M., 2017. Semi-natural habitats support biological control, pollination and soil conservation in Europe: a review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 37 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-017-0434-x>.
- Indoria, A.K., Sharma, K.L., Reddy, K.S., 2020. Hydraulic properties of soil under warming climate. In: Prasad, M.N.V., Pietrzykowski, M. (Eds.), *Climate Change and Soil Interactions*. Elsevier, pp. 473–508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818032-7.00018-7>.
- Jaeger, J.A.G., 2000. Landscape division, splitting index, and effective mesh size: new measures of landscape fragmentation. *Landscape Ecology* 15, 115–130.
- Jastrzebska, M., Szarejko, T., Hoidyński, C., Jastrzebski, W.P., 2009. Species Diversity in Grassland Communities under Different Habitat Conditions. *Polish Journal of Natural Science* 24 (1), 43–59. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10020-009-0005-y>.
- Juventa, S.D., Rossing, W.A., Ditzler, L., van Apeldoorn, D.F., 2021. Spatial and genetic crop diversity support ecosystem service delivery: a case of yield and biocontrol in dutch organic cabbage production. *Field Crops Research* 261, 208015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2020.108015>.
- Keith, D.A., Rodríguez, J.P., Rodríguez-Clark, K.M., Nicholson, E., Aapala, K., Alonso, A., Zambrano-Martínez, S., 2013. Scientific foundations for an IUCN Red list of ecosystems. *PLoS ONE* 8 (5), e62111. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0062111>.
- Keith, H., Czúcz, B., Jackson, B., Driver, A., Nicholson, E., Maes, J., 2020. A conceptual framework and practical structure for implementing ecosystem condition accounts. *One Ecosystem* 5. <https://doi.org/10.3897/oneeco.5.e58216>.
- Keller, T., Lamandé, M., Mojtaba, N.-B., de Lima, R.P., 2022. Soil Compaction due to Agricultural Field Traffic: an Overview of Current Knowledge and Techniques for Compaction Quantification and Mapping. In: Saljnjkova, E., Mueller, L., Lavrishev, A., Eulenstein, F. (Eds.), *Innovations in Landscape Research. Advances in Understanding Soil Degradation*, pp. 287–312.
- Khan, M.M., Bhatt, P., 2023. Editorial: Environmental pollutants in agroecosystem: Toxicity, mechanism, and remediation. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 14, 1208405. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2023.1208405>.
- King, S., Agra, R., Zoloyomi, A., Keith, H., Nicholson, E., de Lamo, X., Brown, C., 2024. Using the system of environmental-economic accounting ecosystem accounting for policy: a case study on forest ecosystems. *Environmental Science & Policy* 152, 103653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103653>.
- Kirch, P., Heinicke, T., Shepherd, G., Zeitz, J., 2016. Application and Verification of Techniques for Visually Assessing Pasture Conditions in Mountainous Terrain: a Test of three Field Assessment Methods in the Kyrgyz Republic. *Mountain Research and Development* 36 (3), 355. <https://doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-15-00049.1>.
- Kwatra, S., Kumar, A., Sharma, P., 2020. A critical review of studies related to construction and computation of Sustainable Development Indices. *Ecological Indicators* 112, 106061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2019.106061>.
- Lange, S., Campagne, C.S., Comte, A., Bank, E., Santos-Martín, F., Maes, J., Burkhard, B., 2022. Progress on ecosystem accounting in Europe. *Ecosystem Services* 57, 101473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101473>.
- Lange, S., Mockford, A., Burkhard, B., Müller, F., Diekötter, T., 2023. As green infrastructure, linear semi-natural habitats boost regulating ecosystem services supply in agriculturally-dominated landscapes. *One Ecosystem* 8, e108540. <https://doi.org/10.3897/oneeco.8.e108540>.
- Little, I.T., Hockey, P.A.R., Jansen, R., 2015. Assessing biodiversity integrity for the conservation of grazed and burnt grassland systems: avian field metabolic rates as a rapid assessment tool. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 24 (6), 1443–1471. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-015-0868-x>.
- Lombardo, U., Iriarte, J., Hilbert, L., Ruiz-Pérez, J., Capriles, J.M., Veit, H., 2020. Early Holocene crop cultivation and landscape modification in Amazonia. *Nature* 581 (7807), 190–193. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2162-7>.
- Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal and Nature Protection Agency, 2011. Naturräumliche Regionen Niedersachsen. Retrieved from https://www.umwelt.niedersachsen.de/service/umweltkarten/natur_landschaft/naturraeumliche_regionen/naturraeumliche-regionen-in-niedersachsen-8639.html.
- LSN, 2024. Bodennutzung und Größenstruktur, Weinbau, Zwischenfrüchte, Bewässerung. Agrarstrukturerhebung in Niedersachsen 2023, No. 2. Retrieved from https://www.statistik.niedersachsen.de/landwirtschaft_forstwirtschaft_fischerei_landwirtschaft_in_niedersachsen/agrarstrukturerhebung_landwirtschaftliche_betriebe/agrarstrukturerhebung-2023-statistische-berichte-236233.html.
- Macura, B., Suskevičs, M., Garside, R., Hannes, K., Rees, R., Rodela, R., 2019. Systematic reviews of qualitative evidence for environmental policy and management: an overview of different methodological options. *Environmental Evidence* 8 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-019-0168-0>.
- Maes, J., Bruzón, A.G., Barredo, J.I., Vallecillo, S., Vogt, P., Rivero, I.M., Santos-Martín, F., 2023. Accounting for forest condition in Europe based on an international statistical standard. *Nature Communications* 14 (3723). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39434-0>.
- Maes, J., Driver, A., Czúcz, B., Keith, H., Jackson, B., Nicholson, E., Dasoo, M., 2020. A review of ecosystem condition accounts: lessons learned and options for further development. *One Ecosystem* 5, e53485. <https://doi.org/10.3897/oneeco.5.e53485>.
- Maes, J., Teller, A., Erhard, M., Grizzetti, B., Barredo, J. I., Paracchini, M. L., Zuilian, A., 2018. *Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services: an analytical framework for ecosystem condition*. Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2779/055584>.
- Markfeld, M., Rotem, G., Ziv, Y., 2022. A network approach for analyzing arthropod diversity and natural patches prioritization in a fragmented agroecosystem. *Landscape Ecology* 37 (6), 1527–1541. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-022-01438-4>.
- Mirghaed, F.A., Sour, B., 2022. Effect of landscape fragmentation on soil quality and ecosystem services in land use and landform types. *Environmental Earth Sciences* 81 (12). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-022-10454-1>.
- Montoya, D., Haegeman, B., Gaba, S., de Mazancourt, C., Loreau, M., 2021. Habitat fragmentation and food security in crop pollination systems. *Journal of Ecology* 109, 2991–3006. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.13713>.
- Moonen, A.-C., Barberi, P., 2008. Functional biodiversity: an agroecosystem approach. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 127 (1–2), 7–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2008.02.013>.
- Moriarty, P.E., Hodgson, E.E., Froehlich, H.E., Hennessey, S.M., Marshall, K.N., Oken, K. L., Stawitz, C.C., 2018. The need for validation of ecological indices. *Ecological Indicators* 84, 546–552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.09.028>.
- Nardo, M., Saisana, M., Saltelli, A., Tarantola, S., Hoffman, A., & Giovannini, E., 2005. *Handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators: Methodology and User Guide* (OECD Statistics Working Papers No. 2005/3).
- Nature, 2020. The United Nations must get its new biodiversity targets right. *Nature* 578, 337–338. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00450-5>.
- Naturkapital Deutschland - TEEB DE, 2016. *Ökosystemleistungen in ländlichen Räumen – Grundlage für menschliches Wohlergehen und nachhaltige wirtschaftliche Entwicklung*. UFZ, Hannover, Leipzig. Retrieved from https://www.ufz.de/export/data/global/190505_TEEB_DE_Landbericht_Langfassung.pdf.
- Niemeijer, D., de Groot, R.S., 2008. A conceptual framework for selecting environmental indicator sets. *Ecological Indicators* 8 (1), 14–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2006.11.012>.
- Niedersächsisches Ministerium für Ernährung, Landwirtschaft, Verbraucherschutz und Landesentwicklung (NML), 2010. *Die Landwirtschaft in Niedersachsen*. Brochure. pp. 48.
- Noss, R.F., 1999. Assessing and monitoring forest biodiversity: a suggested framework and indicators. *Forest Ecology and Management* 115 (1–2), 135–146. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(98\)00394-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(98)00394-6).
- Ofem, B.I., Mchi, A.A., 2023. Variable Conceptualisation and Measurement in Environmental Research. *International Journal of Methodology* 2 (1), 2–11. <https://doi.org/10.21467/ijm.2.1.5991>.
- Olimpi, E.M., Garcia, K., Gonther, D.J., Kremen, C., Synder, W.E., Wilson-Rankin, E.E., Karp, D.S., 2022. Semi-natural habitat surrounding farms promotes multifunctionality in avian ecosystem services. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 59, 898–908. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14124>.
- Page, M.J., Moher, D., Bossuyt, P.M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T.C., Mulrow, C.D., McKenzie, J.E., 2021. Prisma 2020 explanation and elaboration: Updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 372. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>.
- Parajuli, K., Ghimire, P., 2024. Farmland Birds and their Importance in Agroecosystem: a Review. *International Research Journal of MMC* 5 (4), 158–168. <https://doi.org/10.3126/irjmmc.v5i4.70828>.
- Parkhurst, T., Standish, R.J., Prober, S.M., Kobryn, H., Vardon, M., 2024. Balancing the books of nature by accounting for ecosystem condition following ecological restoration. *Scientific Reports* 14 (1), 11369. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-62137-5>.
- Pereira, P., Bogunovic, I., Muñoz-Rojas, M., Brevik, E.C., 2018. Soil ecosystem services, sustainability, valuation and management. *Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health* 5, 7–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2017.12.003>.

- Piqueray, J., Bottin, G., Delescaillie, L.-M., Bisteau, E., Colinet, G., Mahy, G., 2011. Rapid restoration of a species-rich ecosystem assessed from soil and vegetation indicators: the case of calcareous grasslands restored from forest stands. *Ecological Indicators* 11 (2), 724–733. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2010.06.007>.
- Plutino, M., Bianchetto, E., Durazzo, A., Lucarini, M., Lucini, L., Negri, I., 2022. Rethinking the Connections between Ecosystem Services, Pollinators, Pollution, and Health: Focus on Air Pollution and its Impacts. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19 (5), 2997. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19052997>.
- Potschin, M., Haines-Young, R., Heink, U., & Jax, K., 2014. *OpenNESS Glossary (V2.0) Grant Agreement No 308428*. Retrieved from Available from: <http://www.openness-project.eu/library/reference-book>.
- Quintarelli, V., Radicetti, E., Allevato, E., Stazi, S.R., Haider, G., Abideen, Z., Mancinelli, R., 2022. Cover Crops for Sustainable Cropping Systems: A Review. *Agriculture* 12 (12), 2076. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12122076>.
- Renard, D., Tilman, D., 2019. National food production stabilized by crop diversity. *Nature* 571 (7764), 257–260. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1316-y>.
- Rendon, P., Erhard, M., Maes, J., Burkhard, B., 2019. Analysis of trends in mapping and assessment of ecosystem condition in Europe. *Ecosystems and People* 15 (1), 156–172. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2019.1609581>.
- Rendon, P., Steinhoff-Knopf, B., Burkhard, B., 2022. Linking ecosystem condition and ecosystem services: a methodological approach applied to European agroecosystems. *Ecosystem Services* 53, 101387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101387>.
- Rosenfield, M.F., Miedema Brown, L., Anand, M., 2022. Increasing cover of natural areas at smaller scales can improve the provision of biodiversity and ecosystem services in agroecological mosaic landscapes. *Journal of Environmental Management* 303, 114248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114248>.
- Ruiz-Martinez, I., Marraccini, E., Debolini, M., Bonari, E., 2015. Indicators of agricultural intensity and intensification: a review of the literature. *Italian Journal of Agronomy* 10 (2), 74–84. <https://doi.org/10.4081/ija.2015.656>.
- Ryan, C., Case, B.S., Bishop, C.D., Buckley, H.L., 2023. Ecosystem integrity of active sand dunes: a case study to implement and test the SEEA-EA global standard, from Aotearoa New Zealand. *Ecological Indicators* 149, 110172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.110172>.
- Saccà, M.L., Barra Caracciolo, A., Di Lenola, M., Grenni, P., 2017. Ecosystem Services provided by Soil Microorganisms. In: Lukac, M., Grenni, P., Gamboni, M. (Eds.), *Soil Biological Communities and Ecosystem Resilience*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 9–24. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-63336-7_2.
- Sanderson, M.A., 2014. Evaluating the USDA-NRCS pasture condition score system with weighted indicators. *Ecological Indicators* 41, 183–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2014.01.042>.
- Schipanski, M.E., Barbercheck, M., Douglas, M.R., Finney, D.M., Haider, K., Kaye, J.P., White, C., 2014. A framework for evaluating ecosystem services provided by cover crops in agroecosystems. *Agricultural Systems* 125, 12–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2013.11.004>.
- Schmeller, D.S., Weatherdon, L.V., Loyau, A., Bondeau, A., Brotons, L., Brummitt, N., Regan, E.C., 2018. A suite of essential biodiversity variables for detecting critical biodiversity change. *Biological Reviews of the Cambridge Philosophical Society* 93 (1), 55–71. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12332>.
- Schober, P., Boer, C., Schwarte, L.A., 2018. Correlation Coefficients: Appropriate Use and Interpretation. *Anesthesia and Analgesia* 126 (5), 1763–1768. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000002864>.
- Schönwiese, C.-D., 2013. *Klimatologie*, 4th ed. UTB, Stuttgart.
- Schwieder, M., Tetteh, G.O., Blickensdörfer, L., Gocht, A., Stefan, E., 2024. *Agricultural land use (raster): National-scale crop type maps for Germany from combined time series of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and Landsat data (2017–2021)*. Retrieved from: <https://zenodo.org/records/10617623>.
- Sinclair, S.J., Griffioen, P., Duncan, D.H., Millett-Riley, J.E., White, M.D., 2015. Quantifying ecosystem quality by modeling multi-attribute expert opinion. *Ecological Applications: A Publication of the Ecological Society of America* 25 (6), 1463–1477. <https://doi.org/10.1890/14-1485.1>.
- Smith, R.G., Gross, K.L., Robertson, G.P., 2008. Effects of Crop Diversity on Agroecosystem Function: Crop Yield Response. *Ecosystems* 11 (3), 355–366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-008-9124-5>.
- Stockdale, E.A., Murphy, D.V., 2017. Managing Soil Microbial Biomass for Sustainable Agro-Ecosystems. In: Tate, K.R. (Ed.), *Microbial Biomass: A Paradigm Shift in Terrestrial Biogeochemistry*. World Scientific Publishing Europe Ltd., pp. 67–101. https://doi.org/10.1142/9781786341310_0003.
- Tarjuelo, R., Margalida, A., Mougeot, F., 2020. Changing the fallow paradigm: a win-win strategy for the post-2020 Common Agricultural Policy to halt farmland bird declines. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 57 (3), 642–649. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13570>.
- Thapa, R., Mirsky, S.B., Tully, K.L., 2018. Cover Crops Reduce Nitrate Leaching in Agroecosystems: A Global Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 47, 1400–1411. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2018.03.0107>.
- Thomas, J., Harden, A., 2008. Methods for the thematic synthesis of qualitative research in systematic reviews. *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 8, 45. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-8-45>.
- United Nations, European Union, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, International Monetary Fund, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, & The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank (2024). *System of Environmental Economic Accounting - Ecosystem Accounting* (Statistical Papers No. Series F No. 124). New York.
- Vallecillo, S., Maes, J., Teller, A., Babí Almenar, J., Barredo, J.I., Trombetti, M., Gumbert, A., 2022. EU-wide methodology to map and assess ecosystem condition: Towards a common approach consistent with a global statistical standard. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/13048>.
- Voroney, P., 2019. Soils for Horse Pasture Management. In: Sharpe, P. (Ed.), *Horse Pasture Management*. Elsevier, pp. 65–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812919-7.00004-4>.
- Wang, X., Liu, W., Wu, W., 2009. A holistic approach to the development of sustainable agriculture: application of the ecosystem health model. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology* 16 (5), 339–345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504500903106675>.
- Wei, L., Luo, Y., Wang, M., Su, S., Pi, J., Li, G., 2020. Essential fragmentation metrics for agricultural policies: linking landscape pattern, ecosystem service and land use management in urbanizing China. *Agricultural Systems* 182, 102833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2020.102833>.
- Whelan, C.J., Şekercioğlu, Ç.H., Wenny, D.G., 2015. Why birds matter: from economic ornithology to ecosystem services. *Journal of Ornithology* 156 (S1), 227–238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10336-015-1229-y>.
- Williams, P., Biggs, J., Stoate, C., Szczyr, J., Brown, C., [Colin], & Bonney, S., 2020. Nature based measures increase freshwater biodiversity in agricultural catchments. *Biological Conservation* 244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108515>.
- Xu, S., Rowntree, J., Borrelli, P., Hodbod, J., Raven, M.R., 2019. Ecological Health Index: a Short Term monitoring Method for Land Managers to Assess Grazing Lands Ecological Health. *Environments* 6 (6), 67. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments606067>.
- Zhang, W., Ricketts, T.H., Kremen, C., Carney, K., Swinton, S.M., 2007. Ecosystem services and dis-services to agriculture. *Ecological Economics* 64 (2), 253–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2007.02.024>.
- Zhao, G., 2023. Trends in grassland science: based on the shift analysis of research themes since the early 1900s. *Fundamental Research* 3 (2), 201–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fmre.2022.05.008>.
- Zobeck, T.M., Crownover, J., Dollar, M., van Pelt, R.S., Acosta-Martinez, V., Bronson, K.F., Upchurch, D.R., 2007. Investigation of Soil Conditioning Index values for Southern High Plains agroecosystems. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation* 62 (6), 433–442.